

AI·EFFECT

Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility
For the Energy sector

D6.5 Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Interim report

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Table 1 List of AI-EFFECT partners

Number	Legal Name	Acronym	Country
01	EPRI Europe DAC (Coordinator)	EEU	IE
02	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência	INESC TEC	PT
03	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU	DK
04	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	NL
05	Institut de Recherche Technologique SystemX	IRTSX	FR
06	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e. V.	Fraunhofer	DE
07	Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen	RWTH	DE
08	IKIM LTD.	IKIM	IE
09	Maynooth University	NUIM	IE
10	DNV AS	DNV	NO
11	EnliteAI GmbH	ENLITE	AT
12	Watt-IS S.A.	WATT-IS	PT
13	Cooperativa Eléctrica do Vale D'Este CRL	CEVE	PT
14	Bornholms Varme A/S	BHV	DK
15	ENEL GRIDS S.R.L	ENEL	IT
16	E Distribucion redes Digitales (Affiliated Entity)	EDRD	ES
17	Hertie School Gemeinnutzige GMBH	HERTIE	DE
18	Center Danmark Drift APS	CDK	DK
19	Tennet TSO BV (Associated Partner)	TENNET	NL

Executive Summary

The EU-funded AI-EFFECT project seeks to improve access to the tools and facilities required for developing, testing, and validating AI solutions in the energy sector. To achieve this goal, the project will establish an innovative European testing and experimentation infrastructure, built from distributed, virtually connected existing facilities across Europe. In addition, it will create a digital platform designed to ensure interoperability, scalability, and flexibility for both users and resources.

AI-EFFECT will progress through four distinct phases, aligned with its objectives and structured into six work packages (WPs). **WP6**, dedicated to Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication, oversees overall project coordination, including communication activities and stakeholder engagement.

Under Task 6.3: Design and Implementation of Communication and Dissemination Activities, the project focuses on creating and executing effective communication strategies. Task 6.4: Stakeholder Engagement, Community Building, Standardization, and Coordination with Other European Initiatives aims to foster collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and industry to support AI adoption in the energy sector. This deliverable, D6.5 – Dissemination, Communication, and Outreach Activities, updates D6.3 – Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, highlighting progress from M6 to M18 and outlining next steps to expand these efforts. It emphasizes implemented initiatives and its results to promote project's visibility and awareness and stakeholder engagement, aligned with the project communication plan and the communication campaigns roadmap.

1. Introduction

As the digital era reshapes the energy sector, integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into critical infrastructure promises to drive greater efficiency, resilience, and sustainability.

AI-EFFECT will establish a European Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) for AI applications in the energy sector, enabling development, testing, and validation at various stages. It will virtually connect existing European computing and lab facilities through a digital platform, ensuring interoperability, scalability, and secure data exchange.

To achieve the primary objectives and expected outcomes, the AI-EFFECT project is organised into six work packages. WP6 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, addresses the management of the project and all the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities of AI-EFFECT. WP6 has the following objectives:

- 1) Coordinate the actions of participants and monitor the progress of project goals to ensure the delivery of results in a timely, cost-effective way;
- 2) Financial and administrative management, being a reliable interface to the European Commission (EC), the external stakeholders and the public at large;
- 3) Identification and mitigation of project risks by performing effective risk management, managing the project Intellectual Property (IP);
- 4) Ensure maximum project visibility and impact by efficiently communicating project innovations;
- 5) Promote synergies with the energy industry, such as system operators, retailers and producers, as well as with the scientific community, including organizations active in related projects to combine efforts and accelerate dissemination;
- 6) Identify the best exploitation of the project results during and after the project;
- 7) Organise a constant dialogue with the relevant stakeholders.

Under this WP, tasks 6.3 and 6.4 specifically addresses Communication and Dissemination.

Task 6.3 “Design and Implementation of Communication and Dissemination Activities” focuses on delivering engaging, impactful communications and actively sharing project results with key audiences. It includes selecting communication channels, tailoring messages for stakeholders, and defining activities with clear performance indicators.

Task 6.4 “Stakeholder Engagement, Community Building, Standardization, and Coordination with Other European Initiatives” aims to involve stakeholders throughout the project, fostering collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and industry.

The foundations were established with the Dissemination and Communication Plan at M6 (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025), followed by the implementation of the strategy, whose progress is detailed here. This document serves as an interim report on dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement, and project outreach up to M18. The following chapters outline key initiatives that promote continuous learning, best practice sharing, and stakeholder networking, fostering a collaborative ecosystem for policy development and implementation. A final update will be provided at M36.

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1. Communication Objectives

The core principle of AI-EFFECT's C&D activities is to leverage innovative results and key achievements to generate value within target communities and initiatives at the European level and beyond, with the aim to:

1. Raise awareness about the importance of an open distributed Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) to boost the adoption of AI-based solutions in the energy sector;
2. Promote an understanding about the digital tools and technologies that are being developed;
3. Reach and inform the stakeholders of the project, especially the ones in the demonstration areas, while the project is being developed;
4. Ensure broad visibility of the project;
5. Contribute to the creation of synergies with other ongoing and future Horizon EU-supported actions, including other TEFs.

2.2 Key Audiences and Tailored Messages

The analysis of the relevant stakeholders, starting from the already identified Target Groups (TGs) has been carried out and for each stakeholder group a dedicated approach and engagement strategy, including main messages and best communication channels, has been defined.

Several communication messages tailored to each target audience were drafted to clearly and concisely emphasize the significance and benefits of the AI-EFFECT project. These messages have been detailed in D6.3 (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025). They have been targeted using the below mentioned channels.

Table 2 Examples of project tailored messages Table 2 summarizes the key communication messages for each stakeholder group, along with the primary channels used to deliver them.

Table 2 Examples of project tailored messages

Stakeholder Groups	Messages	Primary channel
TG1 Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-EFFECT provides access to unique datasets and real testing environments for proof of concept of new AI methods, enabling R&D community to conduct robust and impactful research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Conferences and webinars.
TG2 Energy Industry, including a) TG2.1: Energy Producers; b) TG2.2: Grid Owner/Operators (DSOs and TSOs); c) TG2.3: Energy Communities; d) TG2.4: Energy Retailers and Aggregators; e) TG2.5: Energy Service Companies (e.g., ESCOs) and Energy Efficiency Consultants;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At AI-EFFECT, we are leveraging advanced AI tools to ensure efficient and reliable grid management and resilience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry events • LinkedIn • Technology Brochures • Newsletter • Podcast • Advisory Board

<p>f) TG2.6: Other Energy Companies.</p>		
<p>TG3 Non-profit Organisations, including</p> <p>a) TG3.1: System Operators Associations (e.g., ENTSO-E, EDSO);</p> <p>b) TG3.2: Consumer Organisations (e.g., ECC-Network);</p> <p>c) TG3.3: Digital Innovation Hubs;</p> <p>d) TG3.4: Environmental Organisations;</p> <p>e) TG3.5: Other Non-Profit.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-EFFECT supports non-profits in advancing their missions through AI-driven energy solutions, ensuring that applications are developed with social and environmental considerations in mind. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release Thematic webinars and events Fact sheets
<p>TG4 Technology Providers, including Companies developing/providing Software (SW) platforms, Hardware (HW) devices, AI tools and applications, Communication networks, Data analytics tools, Cybersecurity solutions, and IoT devices.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test and validate your AI tools in a controlled environment, with near-real data and models ensuring the reliability and effectiveness of your tools. Benefit from established methodologies and KPIs for testing AI products, providing a structured approach to validate your solutions against industry standards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Technology brochures
<p>TG5 General Public and Civil Society, including Individual Energy Consumers, Prosumers and Customers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving everyday life by providing reliable and tested AI energy solutions, ensuring safer, more efficient, and sustainable energy use for all. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press Releases Project videos and infographics Podcasts
<p>TG6 Policy Makers, Regulators and Public Authorities at European, National and Regional levels, including Government and Governmental Agencies.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing a controlled environment, as outlined in the AI Act, for safely developing, testing, and validating AI systems, ensuring compliance with regulations, mitigates risks, and fosters innovation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder roundtables Policy documents/sessions Fact sheets Podcasts
<p>TG7 Standardisation Bodies, including IEC, IEEE, ISO, UNE, CEN, and GBC.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating AI Standardization: AI-EFFECT identifies gaps and provides best practice knowledge, crucial for building trust and ensuring consistent, reliable AI implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working groups Joint workshops

2.3 Communication and Dissemination Tools and Actions

The AI-EFFECT project is utilising four key marketing communication tools to effectively engage with the audience: advertising, digital marketing, public relations, and direct marketing. Each tool involves specific actions tailored to meet distinct objectives and audience targets, as outlined in *Table 3*, contributing significantly to our communication and dissemination initiatives.

Table 3 Communication tools, actions alignment with objectives and target groups

Communication Tool	Action	Objectives	TGs
Advertising	Logo, brochure, poster, roll-up	4. Ensure broad visibility of the project;	All
	Videos	2. Promote an understanding about the digital tools and technologies that are being developed; 3. Reach and inform the stakeholders of the project, especially the ones in the demonstration areas, while the project is being developed; 4. Ensure broad visibility of the project;	All
Digital Marketing	Website	All	All
	Social Media	All	TG1 Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia. TG2 Energy Industry TG4 Technology Providers, TG6 Policy Makers, Regulators and Public Authorities TG7 Standardisation Bodies
Direct Marketing	Newsletter	All	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7
Public relations	Press release	4. Ensure broad visibility of the project	TG3 Non-profit Organisations TG5 General Public and Civil Society
	Events	All	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7

The communication and dissemination approach and strategies can be split into three main bigger groups:

1. **Dissemination towards the scientific community, industry and civil society:** Dissemination towards Target Groups to maximize the visibility of the outcomes. This has been done through submission to scientific journals and presentation and conferences and industry events and will be reinforced with project webinars and workshops.
1. **Communication towards other TEFs:** Knowledge sharing about AI testing and validation, and ethical issues, through the organization of thematic roundtables and workshops.
2. **Communication towards citizens:** Communicate project impacts and expected societal outcomes in plain English, highlighting the benefits of AI and its ethical and social dimensions via various media outlets and the project digital presence.

Table 4 summarizes main communication activities and channels used in the project, the targeted KPIs and impact achieved until M18.

Table 4 Main communication activities and channels and respective KPIs

Communication Activities and Channels	Measurable KPIs and Target	M19
Project Visual Identity: Including the development of a professional-quality project logo together with associated templates for all presentation and marketing collaterals and a service/project motto.	100% of communication materials will be compliant with the project's visual identity and branding.	100% of materials are compliant with the visual identity
Communication Material: Development of infographics, posters/rollups, and flyers/leaflets/postcards that will contain general project information, as well as best practices and ad-hoc information for events.	No. of distributed communication material: > 500 (copies distributed, including printing and download).	150 copies printed 26 downloads
Project Website: It includes all non-disclosure information about the project: general description, relevant publications, public deliverables, partnerships, and events. The website will be updated bi-weekly.	Unique visits: > 1500/year Unique page visits: > 3.000/year No. of downloads: > 70/year	Unique visitors: 3,434 Unique page visits: 4,950 No. of downloads: 44 unique downloads
Social Media: The project will leverage social media platforms for real-time updates, engagement, and community building., especially LinkedIn. which will be critical in engaging with professionals at a European level and raising the profile of the initiative.	LinkedIn: No. of posts: 2 per month No. of impressions: > 300 per post No. of engagement (like/share/ comment): >10 per post	No. of posts: 3 per month No. of impressions: 800 on average per post No. of engagement: 22 on average per post

Newsletter: Stakeholders and a wider audience will be reached through newsletters presenting the project, its objectives, and findings.	No. of newsletters: 6 (2/year) No. of subscribers: > 100	2 No. of subscribers: 191
Technology brochure: Development of a brochure gathering key technical information about the technologies developed (factsheets and specifications).	No. of technical brochures: > 4	1
Promotional Videos: Promotional videos presenting the overall project and part of the tests carried out during the project duration will be prepared.	No. of videos: 3 No. of views: > 300/per video	1 video 355 views
Press Releases: press releases will be issued at key project milestones, or achievements, leading to several news pieces being published in international media outlets about the project.	No. of press releases: 8 No. of media insertions: > 25	3 press releases 7 media insertions
Joint Events, Workshops and Networking: Events organised by experts, researchers, clients, and industry audiences, where project partners will be invited to present their work and vision.	No. of events: 5 No. of participants: > 150	3 events 620 participants
Training Workshops and Webinars: They will target various stakeholder groups to inform them about benefits, best practices, and specific adaptations; for technical/managerial staff, but also public/consumers-oriented events.	No. of training workshops: > 3 No. of webinars: > 5 No. of participants: > 100	0
Podcast: To build awareness, education and understanding about AI in Energy sector, as well as awareness of project progress and engagement among the target audience, especially organizations with varying levels of expertise and interest in the intersection of artificial intelligence and the energy sector.	No. of podcasts: 6 (2/year) No of downloads: >500 (total) Nb of subscribers: >50	2 No downloads: 505 No subscribers: Not Applicable

The monitoring and evaluation of C&D KPIs is an ongoing process. Matomo Analytics is being utilised to assess website performance, while social media KPIs will be tracked using the native analytics tools of the respective platforms. Video performance data has been gathered from social media channels, as well as the newsletter analytics.

Ongoing monitoring allows for strategy adjustments and corrective actions if results do not align with expectations.

In the following subchapters, the progress made within each communication tool and actions will be analysed.

2.3.1 Project Brand Identity

The project brand identity includes the project's name, logo, colour scheme, typography, and overall design style. The brand identity has been developed in M3 of the project and is detailed in (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025).

Figure 1 Different logo representations

2.3.2 Flyer and roll-up banner

The flyer and roll up have been delivered in M3 and details are provided in (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025). No updates have been done since then.

2.3.3 Videos

The project awareness video has been developed in M6 and it was disseminated through project channels with a result of 355 views.

In addition to this video, at least two more will be produced, focused on the demonstration nodes and project results.

2.3.6 Podcast

Podcasts are an impactful way to promote the AI-EFFECT project and engage a wide-ranging audience. To amplify AI-EFFECT's reach, the well-established EPRI Current podcast will host special episodes dedicated to the project. These episodes will feature AI-EFFECT's unique branding and focus on delivering in-depth insights, updates, and discussions about the project's progress and its impact, fostering greater awareness and engagement.

The objectives of the podcast are:

- **Build Awareness:** Educate and inform the audience about AI in the energy sector.
- **Provide Updates:** Keep listeners informed about project progress and milestones.
- **Engage Target Audience:** Connect with organizations and individuals with varying levels of expertise and interest in AI and energy.
- **Communicate with TEF Members:** Share knowledge about AI testing and validation, and discuss ethical issues.

Podcast overview:

- **Number of Episodes:** 6
- **Guests per Episode:** 2 or 3
- **Maximum Duration per Episode:** 25 minutes
- **Distribution Channels:** Project channels, podbean, other podcast platforms and YouTube

This approach not only enhances visibility but also fosters a deeper connection with the audience, ensuring the project's goals and achievements are widely recognized and supported.

The podcasts are planned according to the timeline on *Table 5*.

Table 5 Provisional outline of the six project podcast episodes

Episode	Publishing date	Topics to cover
1	April 2025	Introduction to AI and AI in the Energy Sector: Overview of the project and its use cases.
2	September/ October 2025	Project Framework and Architecture
3	April 2026	TEF's projects discussion
4	October 2026	Project Demonstration Nodes
5	April 2027	Data and AI policies in Europe
6	September 2027	Project outcomes and lessons learned

In the first episode, the podcast explored the AI-EFFECT project and its impact on the energy sector in Europe. The guests, Johanna Vorwerk (Assistant Professor at Technical University of Denmark), Massimo Bolognesi (Engineer at ENEL), and Gianluca Lipari (EPRI Europe), discussed various aspects of AI applications in energy systems. This episode received 289 downloads on Podbean (52. What is the AI EFFECT on Europe's Power Industry?, 2026) and 405 views on YouTube (What is the AI EFFECT on Europe's Power Industry?, 2026).

The second episode explored Work Package 2 of the AI-EFFECT: the architecture and the building blocks that enable distributed nodes across multiple countries, feeding the discussion about interoperability, intellectual property protection, and collaboration as pillars for accelerating AI adoption in the energy sector received 215 downloads on Podbean (Exploring the AI-EFFECT on Europe's Energy Future, 2026) and 184 views on YouTube (Exploring the AI-EFFECT on Europe's Energy Future, 2026)

2.3.7 Public Relations

2.3.7.1 Press Releases

The project first press release was issued in M2 to media outlets in Ireland, Italy and Portugal. Details of the press release insertions in the media are summarized in (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025). Five more press releases aim to be sent until end of the project.

In an effort to amplify the project reach, some partners have also published information on other online channels, as shown in *Table 6*.

Table 6 Other online channels disseminating project information

Channel	Link
TU DELFT website	Advancing AI Integration in the European Energy Sector
EEU website	AI-EFFECT
RWTH website	AI-EFFECT
IKIM	AI-EFFECT: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Europe's Energy Future
INESC TEC	From the lab to the power grid: INESC TEC leads Artificial Intelligence experimentation/

ENLIT articles 2025	AI-EFFECT powering the future of energy with smarter testing
BRIDGE Newsletter Dec 2025	ETIPSNET BRIDGE - Exploring AI's role in energy: The AI EFFECT podcast
ENLIT articles 2026	How AI can be a trusted ally in Europe's energy transition
	Testing facilities and AI-EFFECT: Driving Europe's energy AI strategy

2.3.7.2 Events

Events serve as a crucial platform to engage with our project audience, exchange knowledge, and share findings. We will actively promote presentations at leading scientific conferences and participate in EU and industry events, fairs, and exhibitions. Our strategy includes attending events organized by experts, researchers, clients, and industry audiences, where project partners will be invited to present their work and vision.

Industry Events

Until M18 the project has been represented in thirteen events:

1. November 18, 2024 – RTE AI Day (France)
RTE, the French TSO, hosted a workshop dedicated to AI activities in transmission operations. Adrian Kelly presented AI-EFFECT, its mission, strategy, and structure. The event was well attended, offering both virtual and in-person participation.
2. January 7–9, 2025 – Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Digital Transformation (DX) in Electric Power Summit (California, USA)
Gianluca Lipari introduced the AI-EFFECT project to industry leaders and technology providers, fostering connections for future collaborations.
3. February 2025 – 1st FutureGrid Innovation Summit (Organized by E.DSO)
AI-EFFECT project materials were showcased in the exhibition space of this conference/workshop.
4. March 2025 – BRIDGE General Assembly
Participation in the BRIDGE General Assembly to present and discuss AI-EFFECT progress.
5. April 2025 – EPRI European Workshop Week (Barcelona, Spain)
EEU presented AI-EFFECT during the annual workshop, highlighting project scope, vision, architecture, and use cases in the “AI for Grids” session.
6. June 2025 – The AI Summit (London, UK)
EEU presented AI-EFFECT and other AI energy initiatives at this major AI industry event.
7. June 2025 – CIREN, (Geneva, Switzerland)
Participation in the exhibition area within EEU booth.
8. September 2025 – 24th International Wind & Solar Integration Workshop
AI-EFFECT was featured in the “AI in Power Systems” tutorial, with emphasis on service deployments and German node use cases. Activities on AI explainability and trust assessment were also presented.
9. October 2025 – Gulf Cooperation Council Interconnection Authority AI Workshop (Kuwait)
EPRI Europe presented AI-EFFECT and related AI activities focused on energy applications.
10. October 2025 – ECML PKDD Conference (Porto, Portugal)
Adrian Kelly (EEU) presented AI-EFFECT at this leading European AI/ML conference.
11. October 2025 – Enlit Europe, Bilbao
AI-EFFECT, together with sister initiatives EnerTEF Project and EnergyGuard TEF Project, participated in the speaking session, highlighting how advanced AI technologies are reshaping the future of energy. In addition, it was showcased in EPRI’s booth in the EU projects zone, engaging with the events participants.
12. January 2026 – Supergen Energy Network UK, UK
EPRI Europe presented on the AI-EFFECT work in a workshop targeted to UK engineering specialist universities in Bath, UK.
13. March 2026 – European Workshop Week, Prague
EPRI Europe presented the project framework during the EPRI European Workshop Week session

“Accelerating AI in the Energy Future”. The event joined more than 250 participants from grid operators, generation operators, utilities and other stakeholders.

Participation in these events has been instrumental in advancing AI-EFFECT’s communication and engagement objectives. By presenting at leading scientific conferences such as ECML PKDD, the project strengthens its presence within research and academic communities, fostering knowledge exchange and credibility. Industry-focused workshops and summits, including RTE AI Day and EPRI European Workshop Week, enable direct interaction with energy companies, technology providers, and policymakers, promoting collaboration and adoption of AI solutions. Exhibitions and networking opportunities further support outreach to non-profit organizations and civil society, ensuring inclusivity and transparency. Collectively, these activities enhance stakeholder engagement, disseminate project results, and contribute to building a collaborative ecosystem aligned with AI-EFFECT’s mission of driving innovation and standardization in the energy sector.

Other engagement initiatives

The project will foster collaboration between policymakers, researchers, standardization bodies, and industry stakeholders to co-design frameworks that incentivize, boost, and support the adoption of AI-powered tools and solutions in the energy sector. This collaborative approach ensures that policies are well-informed, practical, and aligned with the needs of all stakeholders. The project has submitted a policy session to the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW 26), under the thematic block Competitive and secure Energy Union, exploring how Europe can build a competitive AI ecosystem to accelerate the energy transition, enhance grid resilience, and foster innovation across utilities, industry, and technology providers. The discussion will highlight lessons from TEFs and collaborative initiatives such as EPRI’s OPAI consortium, which develops open, interoperable AI solutions for grid operations and energy markets. Together, these efforts aim to address fragmented frameworks and unlock AI’s potential for competitiveness and decarbonisation. Dates and detailed agenda of the policy session is yet to be confirmed.

Beyond this, AI-EFFECT will establish knowledge-sharing initiatives, such as webinars, conferences, and online forums, to facilitate dialogue and information exchange among policymakers, researchers, industry stakeholders, and citizens. These initiatives will provide opportunities for continuous learning, dissemination of best practices, and networking among stakeholders, fostering a collaborative ecosystem for policy development and implementation. These initiatives are described in subchapter Dissemination activities.

Communication with other TEFs

The project has partnered with key EU stakeholders to advance discussions on AI, through the organization of thematic roundtables and workshops.

In October 2025, AI-EFFECT Project in collaboration with EPRI and EPRI Europe and other TEFs, EnergyGuard and EnerTEF, organized an **AI roundtable discussion with the European Energy Industry** for the European Commission to discuss the implementation of AI in the power sector.

To further build on the first roundtable, AI-EFFECT was invited to the **Workshop on European AI Foundation Model for Energy Grids, in December 2025, hosted by the European Commission (DG ENER B4).**

The Energy TEFs came together again in February 2026 for the webinar **AI Testing & Validation for the Energy Sector: Use Cases, Challenges, and Real-World Impact**. Energy sector stakeholders face unique challenges when implementing AI. This webinar directly addressed these concerns by presenting practical testing methodologies, validation approaches, and proven case studies. More than 70 attendees gained actionable insights into how TEF services can de-risk their AI initiatives, accelerate time-to-deployment, and ensure compliance while learning from real-world implementations across the energy value chain.

In addition, the project has been in contact with other sectors TEFs, with initial meetings taking place, but no joint activity was successfully delivered to date. This engagement inside and outside the energy sector will be

particularly relevant for knowledge sharing, cross-pollination and technology and regulations standardisation, reduce capital investment and development costs, and ensuring the project sustainability beyond its lifetime.

Engagement will go beyond Europe, reaching international partners and equivalents in USA, Canada, Australia, Middle East, South America, and Asia to establish collaborative opportunities.

The project will also promote clustering activities and meetings with other EU consortia under the umbrella of the *REPowerEU* initiative and other European workgroups, such as BRIDGE Initiative.

This collaborative approach ensures that AI-EFFECT contributes to the broader ecosystem, fostering innovation, standardization, and cost-efficiency in the energy sector.

Communication towards citizens

The Communication towards citizens has been kickstarted by our partner CEVE. With an engagement session with the consumers.

On 27 November 2025, CEVE hosted the first dissemination session of the Vale d’Este Living Lab, an initiative designed to test innovative energy solutions directly with our community. About 45 customers were invited and a smaller number attended and actively participated. During the session, INESC TEC researcher Tomás Fidalgo presented the AI-EFFECT project and the service design for the TEF. This engagement session also helped strengthen interest in the AI-Effect project, with participants showing genuine motivation to join the initiative

2.3.8 Digital Marketing

2.3.8.1 Newsletter

The project aims to deliver two newsletters per year, directly engaging with stakeholders. The newsletters have been following a similar structure to ensure consistency and brand recognition, including different sections to cover all the project outcomes, such as **Cover Story**: Featuring a major milestone, outcome, or news item, accompanied by visuals such as photos, infographics, or videos, latest project **News & Events**: and resources, including scientific publications, deliverables or other project outcomes and reports.

The newsletter is distributed through LinkedIn to all page subscribers. The first newsletter was sent in July 2025, achieving **662 Impressions**, and reaching **340 Members**, with an **8.8%** engagement rate. The newsletter is available on (LinkedIn, 2025).

Figure 2 Cover of first project newsletter

The second project newsletter was sent in December 2025, achieving **357** impressions, and reaching **240** members, with a **10.6%** engagement rate. The newsletter is available on (LinkedIn, 2025).

Figure 3 Cover of second project newsletter

2.4 Communication Campaigns

The AI-EFFECT project is structured into four phases: 1) developing use cases and test methodologies, 2) designing the framework and architecture, 3) building and demonstrating solutions across four nodes, and 4) creating an enduring model aligned with EU regulations. To support these objectives, the communication plan is organized into five campaigns: 1) initial awareness, 2) use cases, 3) architecture, 4) node demonstrations, and 5) final outcomes, each aligned with key milestones. This phased approach ensures targeted messaging, maximizes stakeholder engagement, and enhances project visibility throughout its lifecycle.

The full communication campaign timeline is shown in Figure 4 Communication Campaigns TimelineFigure 4.

COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS TIMELINE			
CAMPAIGNS	M1-12	M13-24	M24 - M36
C1	Initial Awareness		
C2	Use Cases Development		
C3	Framework and Architecture		
C4			Nodes demonstration
C5			Project Sustainability and Final Results

Figure 4 Communication Campaigns Timeline

A complete description of the five communication campaigns can be found in (D6.3: Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, 2025). This document will be focused on the completed or ongoing campaigns, highlighting activities and its outcomes.

2.4.1 Campaign 1: Initial Awareness

The objectives of this campaign were:

- Introduce AI-EFFECT project to key stakeholders and the general public with tailored messages.
- Create awareness about the project's goals, significance, and expected outcomes.
- Establish a foundation for ongoing engagement and support throughout the project.

Key activities led:

- Website and Social Media Launch: Create a project website and establish social media profiles to provide updates, share resources, and interact with stakeholders.
- Press Releases and Media Outreach: Issue press releases and collaborate with media outlets to attract coverage and spark interest in the project.
- Launch of Videos and Communication Materials and channels: Release essential video and materials, including flyers, roll-up banners, and other graphics, to support project communication. Issue first episode podcast providing an overview of the project and first newsletter.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Reach out to target groups (scientific communities, industry, policymakers) through targeted emails, newsletters, and direct communications.

This campaign was targeted at all project stakeholders' groups and was live from month 1 to month 9 (October 2024 – June 2025). Key activities and its impact are summarized in *Table 7* 1st Campaign key activities and performance.

Table 7 1st Campaign key activities and performance.

Key activities	KPIs (for the entire duration of the project)	1 st campaign – M9
Website Launch	Unique visitors: > 1500/year Unique page visits: > 3000/year No. of downloads: > 70/year	1,481 visits 2,551 unique pageviews 26 unique downloads
Social Media Launch	No. of posts/retweets: 1 per week; No. of impressions: > 300 per post; No. of engagements >10 per post	1 post per week. 690 impressions per post on average 22 engagements per post on average
Press Releases and Media Outreach	8 PR 25 media insertions	3 PR 11 media insertions
Videos	No. of videos: 3 No. Of views: > 300/per video	1 video with 355 views
Communication materials	500 copies distributed	150 printed 29 downloads
Newsletter	>100 subscribers	340 subscribers
Podcast episode	No of downloads: >500 (total)	669 downloads/views

2.4.2 Campaign 2: Use Cases Development

The objectives of this campaign were:

- Raise Awareness: Inform stakeholders about the design and implementation of AI-EFFECT use cases, operating framework, and validation tools.
- Educate: Provide detailed information on the functionalities, interfaces, and certification processes involved.
- Collaboration: Mutual share of use cases and datasets with research and academia.

Key activities led:

- Develop Open Education Resources such as flyers and graphics to explain the AI-EFFECT functionalities and framework.
- Organize interactive sessions to demonstrate the use cases and toolbox developed, such as workshops or webinars (still being planned).

This campaign targeted TG1: Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia; TG2: Energy Industry; and TG4: Technology Providers. Initially foreseen for month 9 to month 16 (June 2025–January 2026), the campaign will continue until May 2026 to allow additional time for communicating new results emerging from WP1 and WP2 in a more comprehensive way.

2.4.3 Campaign 3: Framework and Architecture

The objectives of this campaign are:

- Inform: Raise awareness about the design and implementation of the modular architecture for the Cyber-Physical aspects of AI-EFFECT.
- Educate: Provide detailed information on technical requirements, hardware and software tools, and performance criteria.

Key activities planned:

- Content Development: Create detailed materials such as videos, infographics, and technical documents explaining the modular architecture and its components.
- Workshops and Webinars: Host sessions to demonstrate the architecture, interconnection solutions, and data safety tools.
- Engage: with other TEFs and BRIDGE Initiative to gather insights and ensure alignment.

Target Groups

- TG1: Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
- TG2 Energy Industry
- TG4 Technology Providers

Timeline:

- Months 9-24 (June 2025-Sept 2026)

Since Campaign 2 and 3 are partially overlapping, the key activities and KPIs considered below make no distinction between the two.

Table 8 2nd and 3rd Campaign key activities and performance.

Key activities	KPIs (for the entire duration of the project)	2 nd /3 rd campaign: M9-M19
Website	Unique visitors: > 1500/year Unique page visits: > 3000/year No. of downloads: > 70/year	2,767 unique visits 3,771 unique pageviews
Social Media	No. of posts/retweets: 1 per week; No. of impressions: > 300 per post; No. of engagements >10 per post	1 post /week (39 posts total); 720 impressions per post on average; 21 engagements per post on average
Stakeholder Engagement	> 10 cooperations > 3 joint meetings	4 stakeholder engagement activities, including events participation.
Webinar/Workshop	5 workshops or webinars	1 participation in wind and solar integration workshop 2 Project workshop & webinar TBC
Podcast episode	No of downloads: >500 (total)	379 (downloads/views)
Newsletter	>100 subscribers	240 subscribers
OER	> 3 OER	1 OER
Publication in Peer reviewed journals	>10	2 submissions

Finally, campaign four will start on M25 focused on nodes demonstration, and campaign five will start on M30, to outline project sustainability and final results. Both campaign activities and results will be reported in the final communication and dissemination deliverable (M36).

2.5 Dissemination activities

In the project, alongside communication activities, targeted dissemination actions will be implemented to ensure the project generates further impact, supports future research, and opens up potential business opportunities

2.5.1 Project webinars & workshops

In addition to attending events, the project will organize training workshops and webinars. These will target various stakeholder groups to inform them about the benefits, best practices, and specific adaptations of our project. The sessions will cater to both technical/managerial staff and the general public/consumers.

Organised or planned webinars and workshops are described next.

- **Webinar 1: Scientific Demonstrations of Explainability & Verification Services**

The project is planning a 60 minutes webinar to be hosted in Q2 2026. This webinar will present the scientific foundations and practical demonstrations of explainability and verification services developed in WP1. The session will showcase methodologies, algorithms, and implementation results that support trust, transparency, and validation across AI pipelines. By sharing concrete outputs, the webinar aims to support collaboration with ongoing and upcoming research projects and position AI-EFFECT as a reference platform for explainable and verified AI services. The target audience of this is research institutions, academic partners, PhD students, scientific staff, other EU projects/TEFs.

- **Seminar: Designing the Best Possible Test & Experimentation Facility (TEF)**

This seminar explores the essential properties of a high-quality AI Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF), covering design principles, reliability requirements, validation processes, and operational models. Building on insights from Task 1.2 and examples from AI-EFFECT, the session will highlight best practices for creating robust and effective test environments that support trustworthy AI development and evaluation. It is planned for Q2 of 2026.

- **Workshop: AI-EFFECT Service Capabilities - Dialogue with Industry**

This hands-on workshop introduces the service capabilities developed in AI-EFFECT and invites industry representatives to discuss their needs, expectations, and challenges regarding AI testing, validation, and integration. Participants will explore how AI-EFFECT services could support real use cases and identify additional requirements to guide future development. The session is built around open dialogue, practical examples, and partner engagement.

It is targeted at industry, especially, grid operators, technology providers, AI vendors and industry associations. It is planned for Q4 2026.

2.5.2 Scientific Publications

Several scientific publications are in the pipeline for submission although no publication has been accepted up to the date of this deliverable. Nonetheless, the AI-EFFECT project is committed to fully supporting open science practices, The project will actively pursue Open Access (OA) publishing, using a dedicated budget for Gold OA and leveraging transformative agreements for Green OA. The project has been publishing its deliverables openly in Zenodo and project website and has a GitHub public repository (AI-EFFECT , 2026) for work developed under the project.

Project materials, including deliverables, open access publications, and general information, will be available on the project website. These materials will be regularly updated and promoted through the project's

communication channels, engaging all relevant target groups, including citizens, civil society, and end-users, in the co-creation process of innovation agendas.

2.5.3 Open Educational Resources

The Open Educational Resources (OER) will support education and training on the functionalities and framework developed as part of the project. These include technical sheets, infographics, videos and other materials.

A **technology brochure and four fact sheets** were designed, summarizing the AI-EFFECT use cases and showing how they demonstrate the unique capabilities of the TEF and its digital platform. It presents:

- The focus of each use case;
- The services used by TEF use cases;
- The business proposition that each use case will serve.

The brochure is targeted at Researchers and Academia working on AI or energy innovation; Energy Industry Stakeholders needing reliable, validated AI solutions; and Technology Providers developing AI tools for utilities or energy communities.

Figure 5 Screenshot of two fact sheets

The full brochure is available in Appendix 1 Use Cases Brochure

Table 9 outlines the KPIs for each dissemination activity and its status by M18.

Table 9 Dissemination KPIs and Target Values

Dissemination Activities and Channels	KPI	Achievement at M18
Publications in peer-reviewed OA scientific journals, potentially including IEEE Transactions and journals, ENERGY, SEGAN, IJEPES, EPSR.	> 10 OA journal publications	0 (two submitted)
Presentations in high profile scientific conferences.	> 12 presentations, reaching > 1000 academics	2 presentations, reaching >200 academics
EU and Industry events, Fairs and Exhibitions , including EU Innovation Days, Enlit, EUSEW, Innogrid, CIRED, and IEEE T&D	> 6 events, > 600 experts	2 participations
Joint Meetings and clustering with other EU consortia under the umbrella of the <i>REPowerEU</i> initiative and other European workgroups	> 5 cooperations > 3 joint meetings	3 cooperations
Standards, Technical Committees and Regulations contributions	> 3 contributions	0 (expected at the end of the project lifetime)
Replication Advisory Group establishment to foster replication beyond the consortium	> 5 members from all partner countries	Replication Advisory Group members have been invited and the project is awaiting confirmation
Site Visits or other forms of direct demonstration of outcomes at demo sites	> 10 companies > 100 visitors	0 (site visits will be planned from M25, when the nodes activities intensify)
Best Practices and Recommendations Manual for industry and policymakers	> 1 handbook	Expected end of the project
Workshops, Webinars and Open Educational Resources (OER)	> 5 workshops or webinars; > 3 OER	2 webinars and 1 workshop planned; 1 OER published.

3. Conclusion

The AI-EFFECT project is poised to drive energy transition through AI experimentation.

The D6.5 Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities - Interim report acts as an interim report of the communication and dissemination efforts since M6 of the project, detailing in each planned communication action what was the result achieved.

The communication plan and KPIs remain on track, particularly given that they are designed to span the full duration of the project. It is worth highlighting the consortium's strong presence during this period, with participation in 13 events, as well as the high quality of engagement achieved—especially in activities led by the European Commission. In addition, our participation in Enlit has provided significant visibility and strong outreach within the European energy ecosystem. The synergies emerging with the TEFs further strengthen the outlook for the next stages, with several joint activities already in preparation. Finally, the planned policy session reinforces the strategic importance of the project and provides a valuable platform to showcase its outcomes and support broader take-up.

Continuous monitoring and updating of this plan will be essential to adapt to the project's progress and ensure that its objectives (enhancing stakeholder awareness, trust, and participation in AI advancements) are fully achieved. Consequently, and as a follow up of this deliverable, a final report on dissemination and communication activities, stakeholder's engagement, and project's outreach is planned for M36.

Ultimately, the AI-EFFECT project aims to boost efficiency, resilience, and sustainability in the European energy ecosystem, by integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into critical energy infrastructure.

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Appendix

Appendix 1 Use Cases Brochure

AI · EFFECT
DRIVING ENERGY TRANSITION THROUGH AI EXPERIMENTATION

Project Use cases brochure

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AI · EFFECT
Project Use cases

Introducing the AI-EFFECT Use Cases

What is AI-EFFECT?

AI-EFFECT is building a European Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) dedicated to Artificial Intelligence solutions for the energy sector. This TEF will allow innovators to develop, test, and validate AI tools at different stages: from early prototypes to near-market technologies.

To do this, AI-EFFECT connects Europe's existing computing and laboratory infrastructures through a digital platform. This virtual network ensures interoperability, secure data exchange, and scalable testing conditions. A core goal of the project is to create and validate **strategic use cases**, developed and tested across four European research nodes.

Why this brochure?

This brochure summarises the AI-EFFECT use cases and shows how they demonstrate the unique capabilities of the TEF and its digital platform. It presents:

- The focus of each use case;
- The services used by TEF use cases;
- The business proposition that each use case will serve.

Who is this for?

- Researchers and Academia working on AI or energy innovation;
- Energy Industry Stakeholders needing reliable, validated AI solutions;
- Technology Providers developing AI tools for utilities or energy communities.

1

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

About the Nodes and the Use Cases

AI-EFFECT operates through four specialised demonstration nodes, each focused on a key energy challenge. Every node hosts at least one TEF Test Use Case, supported by a mix of real-world datasets and synthetic data. The selected nodes and use cases are designed to address real-world challenges faced by European utilities, operators, and consumers, ensuring that outcomes are directly relevant and applicable.

2

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

Danish Node District Heating and Sector Coupling

TEF service backbone of experimentation	TEF Test Use Case validation pipeline to test Business Use Case	TEF Business Case real-world AI application in energy, demonstrating the effectiveness of Use Case
 Explainability analysis	AI Models are analyzed to ensure that their predictions are explainable and interpretable, using techniques like Shapley values to assess how much features impact the predictions.	Forecasting: These use cases focus on predicting energy demand and generation to support proactive and efficient system operation. All these use cases benefit from shared infrastructure and data services
 Mathematical verification	AI Tools are rigorously tested against defined constraints to obtain mathematical performance guarantees or detect unrealistic outputs.	All these use cases benefit from shared infrastructure and data services
 Lab-based testing	Conducted at DTU's SYSLAB, this service allows AI tools to be tested in a controlled physical environment simulating real multi-energy systems	Control: These use cases apply AI to dynamically adjust system parameters.
 Living-lab testing	AI tools are evaluated using real-world data from the energy grid operators BEOF and TREFOR, enabling a comparison of predicted setpoints with actual system behavior.	Operational Optimization: These use cases aim to improve the overall efficiency and sustainability of energy system operations.

3

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

Dutch Node

Transmission System
Congestion Management

TEF service backbone of experimentation	TEF Test Use Case validation pipeline to test Business Use Case	TEF Business Case real-world AI application in energy, demonstrating the effectiveness of Use Case
Data synthetization	Testing and refinement of AI-based algorithms for congestion management. An AI tool addressing this use case should provide decision support for the human operator of the TSO in form of redispatch actions or switching actions that change the topology of the transmission systems.	Congestion Management: Support TSOs in the operation of the transmission system with AI-powered algorithms for decision-making in congestion management.
Benchmarking		
Human-AI interaction		

4

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

German Node

DER Integration in
Distribution System

TEF service backbone of experimentation	TEF Test Use Case validation pipeline to test Business Use Case	TEF Business Case real-world AI application in energy, demonstrating the effectiveness of Use Case
Data Provision	Set up a realistic but risk-free simulation of an electrical distribution grid with high renewable penetration to test and benchmark AI-based congestion management. AI agents observe simulated grid states and propose corrective actions such as redispatching generation, curtailing loads, topology reconfiguration, or adjusting transformer taps to prevent congestion, maintain voltage within limits, and respect environmental constraints.	Operational Optimization: Enable DSOs to maintain reliable, high-quality service on distribution networks with growing DERs and loads by proactively managing congestion. AI supports operational decisions to anticipate and mitigate overloads within operational and environmental constraints, allowing renewable integration, and reduced outages.
AI-Benchmarking		
Explainability Analysis		
Mathematical Verification		

5

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

Portuguese Node

Energy Community
Data Space

TEF service backbone of experimentation	TEF Test Use Case validation pipeline to test Business Use Case	TEF Business Case real-world AI application in energy, demonstrating the effectiveness of Use Case
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Provision AI-Benchmarking 	<p>Performance evaluation of AI-powered Virtual Energy Manager, exploring integration of AI-powered tools to promote energy efficiency in households.</p> <p>Performance evaluation of energy-sharing mechanism within an energy community.</p>	<p>AI-powered Virtual Energy Manager tool to support residential users in improving energy efficiency.</p> <p>AI-based optimization of energy-sharing in energy communities.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Provision & Synthetization AI-Tool Benchmarking Mathematical Verification Simulation Based Testing Lab based Testing 	<p>Testing of DER scheduling/control algorithms, addressing technical challenges and operational constraints.</p>	<p>Voltage control with DER: detect, prevent, or mitigate voltage violations in LV grids.</p> <p>Edge load control for flexibility services, enabling the provision of grid services and participation in flexibility markets.</p>

6

AI-EFFECT Project Use cases

Portuguese Node (continuation)

Energy Community
Data Space

TEF service backbone of experimentation	TEF Test Use Case validation pipeline to test Business Use Case	TEF Business Case real-world AI application in energy, demonstrating the effectiveness of Use Case
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Provision and Synthetization Knowledge Store AI-Tool Benchmarking Feature Importance Analysis Mathematical Verification 	<p>Validation of Load and RES forecasting algorithm: focuses on validating and improving the performance of AI-based Load and Renewable Energy Source forecasting algorithms for energy management.</p>	<p>Load and RES Generation forecasting, supporting energy management and decision making in households and energy communities.</p> <p>Forecasting Electric Vehicle charging patterns, supporting energy management and decision making in EV charging stations.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Provision and Synthetization AI-Tool Benchmarking Virtual Facility Access Simulation-based Testing 	<p>Performance evaluation of network monitoring algorithms. centered around evaluating and improving AI-based network monitoring algorithms in low-voltage (LV) distribution grids.</p>	<p>State estimation and Network Quality: AI estimates voltage and power flows under partial observability, supporting system reliability and quality.</p> <p>Network Topology Estimation: AI models to infer missing or incorrect topology and cable characteristics.</p>

7

AI · EFFECT
DRIVING ENERGY TRANSITION THROUGH AI EXPERIMENTATION

**Full report:
D1.1 - Design of AI-EFFECT
Use Cases and Outputs**

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